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A Decline in Stomatal Conductance Is the Primary Reason for Low Photosynthesis in Veteran Pedunculate Oak Trees

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Abstract: Veteran trees are important elements in forests, as well as urban and suburban areas, and represent part of our cultural heritage. However, increasing age also brings a reduction in vitality. Information on tree physiological vitality can be gained by examining ecophysiological traits, such as photosynthesis, stomatal conductance, and leaf water potential. Here, we assess the effects of age on the photosynthesis and water status of 600-year-old pedunculate oak trees (*Quercus robur* L.) by comparing them with neighbouring 25-year-old trees. While gas exchange measurements indicated lowered photosynthesis in old trees, their maximum rates of Rubisco carboxylation and electron transport were similar to younger trees, suggesting that biochemical limitations to photosynthesis are not the reason behind their reduced vitality. Moreover, there was no difference in light-adapted and dark-adapted chlorophyll fluorescence between old and young trees. In contrast, stomatal conductance (under unlimited soil water availability) was lower, indicating increased stomatal limitations to photosynthesis in veteran trees. On the other hand, high water potential during mild summer drought conditions indicated better access to soil water in old trees, while stomatal conductance in old trees was higher than in young trees at night. A reduced ability to open and close stomata may be one of the reasons for the observed decline in veteran tree vitality, with a lowered ability to regulate stomatal conductance resulting in reduced carbon gain and unnecessarily high water loss.

Keywords: photosynthesis; stomatal conductance; leaf water potential; age-related decline; veteran trees; *Quercus robur* L.

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1. Introduction

Age-related changes in the physiological processes of trees have been a fundamental problem for forest biologists and plant physiologists for many years [1–3]. The aging of trees brings pronounced changes in leaf-level gas exchange and foliar structure [4,5], hormonal regulation [6,7], allocation to reproduction [8], and wood anatomy [9], all of which may contribute to a decline in the tree's vitality. Understanding the underlying mechanisms of tree decline is crucial for predicting the response of old trees to anthropogenically induced environmental changes such as drought stress [10], repeated wildfires, or insect attack [11–13]. The study of age-related growth in trees is often complicated by the loss of the oldest and largest trees in forests as a result of forest management and uncontrolled logging [14–17]; indeed, there has been a dramatic decline in populations of large old trees across the world [18]. This pattern is even clearer with regard to deciduous trees, which show markedly lower longevity than conifers [19]. In Europe, the oldest known deciduous hardwood trees belong to the families *Fagus* (common beech *Fagus sylvatica* L., with individuals of 620 and 622 years of age being known [20]) and *Quercus* (sessile oak *Quercus petraea* (Matt.) Liebl.), with individuals of 934 years of age confirmed [21]. Overall, however, forest trees only rarely achieve ages of 600 to 700 years [22].

Very old, potentially senescent trees, also known as veteran or ancient trees [22,23], show physiological and morphological features distinct from those of young and mature

trees that are related to their (final) stage of ontogenetic development [19]. With increasing age, distinct changes occur in the structure of *Quercus* sp. [24], with old oaks characterised by a large trunk diameter of up to 2 m [19] with significant evidence of decay and dead wood [25]. Newly formed sapwood in such large-diameter trees will be spread more thinly around the expanding trunk, leading to decreased conduction of photosynthetic assimilates to the trunk and roots. Further, the crowns of old pedunculate oaks (*Quercus robur*) usually have just a few large branches bearing relatively sparse foliage [26], resulting in a low ratio of foliage to woody tree structures [27], while other trees may show epicormic branching in the lower part of the crown while the top branches often die [28]. Such age-related changes in crown architecture strongly influence hydraulic conductance throughout the tree [29].

The effects of ontogenetic changes on tree photosynthetic capacity were initially investigated in relation to the ‘hydraulic limitation hypothesis’ [30], which states that, owing to longer hydraulic pathways and, therefore, lower water potential (Ψ), the leaves of taller and older trees experience carbon limitation via reduced stomatal conductance (g_s). While such an age-related decline in g_s and net CO_2 assimilation rate (A) has been confirmed in conifers [31–33], no such clear decline has been observed as yet in deciduous species, despite g_s also decreasing with age [5]. Ref. [34], for example, notes that, during their research, g_s declined with age in two Mediterranean oak sp., while net A did not change. More recently, a fundamentally different idea has emerged that hypothesises that hydraulic limitation in tall and old trees acts as a long-term constraint on the development of leaves, rather than a stress-like mechanism that triggers stomatal closure [1]. Furthermore, as a result of adaptation to greater heights and increasing water stress, the leaves of aged and tall trees develop substantial plastic changes in their leaf functional biology to compensate for this stress [1,9]. Several comparative studies have shown that leaf trait characteristics, such as thickness, density, surface area, mass area, and nitrogen content, may vary with ontogenetic stage [35–39]. In contrast, ref. [40] has shown that the leaf cellular structures of ancient (>2000 years) and young (<50 years) cypress (*Oriental arborvitae Platycladus orientalis* (L.) Franco) trees do not differ. These direct and indirect (i.e., by different water supply) age-dependent traits affect carbon assimilation through volume changes between the intercellular air space and carboxylation sites in chloroplasts, the mesophyll area to total area, stomatal positioning [4,33,36,39], and mesophyll conductance to CO_2 [41], as well as photosynthesis biochemistry, including the maximum rates of Rubisco carboxylation ($V_{c_{\max}}$) or electron transport (J_{\max}) [42,43].

It can be difficult to distinguish between age-related and size-related changes in tree physiology [5,36,40], especially when measurements have been conducted on the height gradient of a tree, making it impossible to disentangle the effects of size from age. Moreover, studies on the physiology of aging (e.g., gas exchange, leaf morphology, and anatomy) have mainly been focused on conifers. Nevertheless, hardwood trees often differ from conifers, particularly in regard to the lack of any strong pattern in age-related decline in A [4]. Ref. [5] has reported that the photosynthetic capacity of temporal deciduous trees shows a hump-shaped pattern, with peaks at intermediate ontogenetic stages, highlighting the importance of considering ontogenetic stage in studies where age-related changes in A are likely to be radically different between mature trees and seedlings/saplings, as well as and mature and senescent trees.

To date, most research on changes in leaf-level gas exchange with age in hardwood trees has focussed on the differences between seedlings and mature specimens, with just a few studies considering other ontogenetic stages [5,25]. Furthermore, most studies have focused on conifers. The aim of this study was to compare A , g_s , and Ψ in pedunculate oaks at two widely different ontogenetic stages, i.e., young trees of around 25 years of age and senescent trees of over 600 years of age. We hypothesise that (i) old oaks will have higher (less negative) leaf Ψ due to a deeper, developed root system with better access to soil water and a presumed higher root-to-leaf surface area ratio; (ii) underlying photosynthesis biochemistry will differ between the two groups due to both age-related changes and differences in foliage development under different levels of water availability; and (iii) g_s

will differ between old and young trees, with higher g_s in old trees as they have better access to soil water and a lower leaf-to-root area ratio.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Site Description

Ecophysiological parameters, i.e., g_s , Ψ , chlorophyll fluorescence, and gas exchange photosynthesis, were assessed in solitary 600-year-old pedunculate oaks growing on flat land surrounded by meadow (the GPS coordinates of a group of two trees are 48.7047231° N, 18.0957931° E, while another two old trees were growing 100 and 210 m to the north), and 25-year-old oaks growing ca 400 m to the south-west on the south-facing edge of a nearby forest (48.7029061° N, 18.0909867° E) in the Kulháň nature reserve, Trenčín region, west Slovakia. The mean diameter at breast height was 13 cm and corresponding height was 12 m in the young trees, while the diameter of the old trees exceeded 100 cm with heights of approximately 20 m. For both age groups, measurements were performed, if possible, on illuminated foliage from the south (or east or west, depending on the distribution of the accessible branches at the bottom of the crown in the old trees)-facing part of the crown, 2–3 m above ground level. Leaves, which were visually fully developed, were selected from proleptic branches. The measurements were conducted on 7 July and 17 September 2015. In total, four old trees and ten young trees were measured in July and three old and three young trees in September, with the order in which the trees were measured being random.

Both sites had illimerised brown soils and similar environmental conditions, being situated within a mild and moderately warm climate region with an average annual temperature of 9.3 °C (highest temperatures in July (average 19.8 °C) and coldest in January (av. −2.5 °C)) and an average annual precipitation of 620–660 mm (highest precipitation between June and July, lowest in January), with approx. 350 mm of rain falling during the growing season (April–September) and 290 mm during the off-season (October–March). Air temperature and humidity were measured at a height of 2 m above the ground, 1 km from the trees, using a Minikin RTH smart sensor (EMS Brno, Brno, Czech Republic). The average daily air temperature and humidity were 26.3 °C and 63%, respectively, on 7 July and 22.4 °C and 72% on 17 September.

2.2. Gas Exchange Measurements

The light-saturated photosynthesis (A_{sat} ; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) of lower canopy leaves was measured using an LI-6400 Portable Photosynthesis System (LiCor Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA), with a reference CO_2 concentration of 400 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ and illumination set to 1500 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Other environmental variables, such as relative humidity and air temperature, corresponded to those measured directly on the day of measurement.

2.2.1. Light and A-C_i Photosynthesis Curves

The response of A (net CO_2 assimilation rate) to light intensity (photosynthesis light curves) and the response of A to intercellular CO_2 concentration (C_i ; A-C_i curves) were measured using the LI-6400 Portable Photosynthesis System (LiCor Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA), according to the user-set automatic program. Light curve measurements started at a photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) intensity of 1500 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, decreasing gradually to 1000, 500, 250, 120, 60, 30, 15, and 0 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The measurement of A-C_i curves was conducted at a reference CO_2 concentration of 400 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$, followed by 100, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 800, 1000, 1500, and 400 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$, under saturating light conditions of 1500 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Leaf chamber air temperature and relative humidity were maintained at 25 °C and 50%, respectively. All measurements were undertaken on 17 September between 8:50 and 15:10. $V_{c_{\text{max}}}$ and J_{max} , standardised to a reference temperature of 25 °C, were estimated using the approach of Sharkey et al. (2007) [44]. The increasing leg of the sequence of $[\text{CO}_2]$ (i.e., 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 800, 1000, and 1500 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$) was used for the calculation. The constants for the parameterization were set as the default of the spreadsheet, and their values for 25 °C were $K_c = 27.24 \text{ Pa}$, $K_o = 16.58 \text{ kPa}$, and

$\Gamma^* = 3.74$ Pa; day respiration and mesophyll conductance were constrained to be higher than zero $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and less than $30 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{Pa}^{-1}$, respectively, and they were estimated by the parameterization. All points below C_i 220 ppm were assigned as Rubisco-limited, for the next two concentrations the limit was not assigned, the following points were assigned as RuBP regeneration-limited, and the last point as TPU limited.

2.2.2. Stomatal Conductance

For both tree age groups, measurement of g_s ($\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) was carried out on three leaves from each tree on 7 July using an AP4 porometer (Delta-T Devices Ltd., Cambridge, UK), with the first measurement being taken at night (4:00 local time), followed by four measurements during the day at 9:00, 12:00, 14:00, and 17:30. The corresponding light intensities, as estimated by a light sensor on the AP4 porometer, were $0, 209 \pm 65, 640 \pm 395, 394 \pm 233,$ and $108 \pm 91 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in old trees and $0.5 \pm 1.5, 158 \pm 30, 892 \pm 652, 241 \pm 213,$ and $31 \pm 15 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in young trees at 4:00, 9:00, 12:00, 14:00, and 17:30, respectively. No significant differences were observed by *t*-tests between the old and young trees at any of the light intensities.

2.3. Chlorophyll Fluorescence

Chlorophyll fluorescence intensity was measured on dark-adapted leaves at night (3:00 local time) using a MINI-PAM fluorometer (Heinz Walz GmbH, Effeltrich, Germany). The nighttime data were then used to calculate the maximum quantum efficiency of PSII photochemistry, i.e., the ratio between variable and maximum fluorescence (F_v/F_m ; see Maxwell and Johnson, 2000) [45]. The dependence effective photochemical quantum yield of PSII (Φ_{PSII}) on PAR was then calculated using PAR intensities of 0, 90, 150, 220, 300, 430, 580, 860, and $1240 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

2.4. Water Potential

Leaf Ψ was measured on 7 July, predawn (4:00) and during the day at 9:00, 12:00, 14:00, and 17:30 using a Scholander pressure chamber (PMS 1000, PMS Instrument, Albany, OR, USA), according to the methodology described by Turner (1988) [46]. Each leaf was taken preferably from the sunlit part of the crown and placed in the pressure chamber immediately after cutting.

2.5. Statistical Methods

The Shapiro–Wilk test was performed on all data to confirm normality; where the assumption of normality or the homogeneity of variance was violated, the non-parametric Mann–Whitney test was used instead. The *t*-test was used to determine the average values and standard deviation for the young and old tree groups, as well as the differences between the two groups. Two-factor analysis of variance, with a significance level of α 0.05, was used to identify the differences between more than two sets of data. Finally, the Holm–Šidák test was used for multiple comparisons between tree age groups. All data were statistically evaluated using SigmaPlot v. 12.3 software (Systat, Inc., San Jose, CA, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Photosynthesis Light Response

There was a clear difference in photosynthesis between the young and old oaks, with the A_{sat} of the young trees being significantly higher at all PAR intensities $\geq 500 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, with the difference increasing as PAR intensity increased up to $1500 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ ($p < 0.001$; Figure 1). In comparison, there was no significant difference in dark respiration between the two groups (young = $1.36 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, old = $1.37 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, mean \pm standard error, $n = 3$; $p > 0.05$).

Figure 1. Light response curves of photosynthesis for young and old oak trees. P points show average photosynthesis values and bars represent standard error. PAR = photosynthetically active radiation, A = photosynthesis rate. Asterisks indicate significant differences between old and young trees (** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$, $n = 3$).

3.2. Chlorophyll Fluorescence

Tree age had no significant effect on the chlorophyll fluorescence parameters of either dark-adapted (F_v/F_m) or illuminated leaves (Φ_{PSII}), with an average F_v/F_m (mean \pm standard error of mean, $n = 4$ in old trees and 10 in young trees) of 0.797 ± 0.001 for old oaks and 0.788 ± 0.003 for young oaks and no observable difference at any light intensity for Φ_{PSII} ($p > 0.05$; Figure 2).

Figure 2. Dependence of quantum yield of PSII (Φ_{PSII}) on photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) for old and young oaks. Points represent average Φ_{PSII} , bars represent standard error ($n = 4$ in old trees and 10 in young trees).

3.3. Dependence of Photosynthesis on CO₂ Concentration (A-C_i Response)

There was no significant difference in $V_{C_{max}}$ and J_{max} , estimated from A-C_i response curves, between the old and young trees ($p > 0.05$; Table 1, Figure 3).

Table 1. Average biochemical parameters values for old and young pedunculate oaks. $V_{C_{max}}$ = Ru-bisco carboxylation rate, J_{max} = electron transport. Values are mean and standard error ($n = 3$).

Parameters	Old	Young	<i>p</i> -Value
$V_{C_{max}}$	94.7 ± 46.4	93.9 ± 9.0	0.981
J_{max}	116.3 ± 37.3	123.0 ± 8.6	0.817

Figure 3. Dependence of photosynthesis (A) on intercellular concentration of CO₂. Data were pooled for three old and three young oak trees.

3.4. Stomatal Conductance

There was a clear difference in g_s between the young and old trees. In the morning, the young trees displayed significantly higher g_s than the old trees, with maximum daytime g_s values of 0.12 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ (range 0.055–0.16 mol m⁻² s⁻¹) in the old trees and 0.28 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ (range 0.23–0.39 mol m⁻² s⁻¹) in the young trees ($p < 0.05$). At night, however, the g_s in the young trees was significantly lower than that in the old oaks (Figure 4), with a minimum g_s of 0.045 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ (range 0.023–0.071 mol m⁻² s⁻¹) in the old trees and 0.016 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ (range 0.013–0.022 mol m⁻² s⁻¹) in the young trees ($p < 0.001$). At noon and in the afternoon the g_s was similar in both groups of trees.

3.5. Leaf Water Potential

The Ψ was always higher (less negative) in the old trees both during night and day (Figure 5), with predawn Ψ being significantly higher in the old trees (avg. old = -0.36 ± 0.23 MPa, young = -0.6 ± 0 MPa; $p < 0.001$). The minimum Ψ was recorded for the young oaks at midday, with the difference compared to the old oaks at the same time being significant (avg. old = -2.25 ± 0.25 , young = -2.68 ± 0.208 MPa; $p < 0.05$).

Figure 4. Stomatal conductance of young and old trees. Asterisks indicate significant differences between old and young trees (* = $p < 0.05$, *** = $p < 0.001$, $n = 4$ in old trees and 10 in young trees), error bars represent standard error.

Figure 5. Water potential of old and young pedunculate oaks. Points represent mean water potential and bars represent standard error ($n = 4$ in old trees and 10 in young trees).

4. Discussion

Our results show that A_{sat} was lower in old oak trees, with greatest difference recorded at maximum PAR, presumably due to increased stomatal limitations in older trees (Figure 1). Similar results for chlorophyll fluorescence indices (Figure 2) and biochemical photosynthesis parameters (Table 1) suggest that pedunculate oaks are capable of maintaining optimal light and carbon photosynthesis reactions into old age (senescence). In contrast, $V_{C_{\text{max}}}$ and J_{max} have been shown to decrease with age in conifers [32,33]. In our study, the maximum quantum photosystem II efficiency (i.e., F_v/F_m) was 0.8, indicating that

the foliage remained healthy and undamaged and had not been subjected to any major stress [47]. To date, the few studies that have focused on trees at different ontogenetic stages (including veteran trees) have also shown that extreme age does not significantly affect ultra-anatomical leaf structure or photosystem II functioning [7,40]. Similar to our own results, ref. [7] reported no significant differences in Fv/Fm or photosynthetic capacity between 20-year-old, 200-year-old, and 600-year-old *Ginkgo biloba* L. trees. The similar underlying photosynthesis biochemistry in young and old age groups indicated by our study confirms that pedunculate oaks are capable of maintaining ‘young’ internal processes even into old age, presumably as they evolve mechanisms that support a high vascular cambium capacity for continuous growth and the expression of disease-resistance genes to maintain longevity [7,48].

The age-related decline in A_{sat} in our study was accompanied by a decrease in g_s . Temperate deciduous trees are characterised by a hump-shaped change in A and g_s during ontogeny, with both A_{sat} and g_s increasing until the tree reaches the reproductive stage, following which they gradually decrease [5,49]—a pattern consistent with our own results. It is assumed that this ontogenetic decrease in photosynthesis capacity occurs due to an increase in the ratio of leaf area to sapwood area, and a decrease in leaf and trunk water conductivity with age [50,51]. On the other hand, ref. [2] has suggested that increases in A and/or g_s with tree age can occur in larger trees as they are better able to tap groundwater thanks to their deeper root systems. Our results demonstrate that access to water (hypothesis 1) was indeed better in the old trees, as indicated by their predawn leaf water potential. Furthermore, Ψ was less negative in the old trees during both daylight and night (Figure 5), again supporting the hypothesis of better access to soil water. This difference in daytime Ψ between young and old trees could have several explanations, one being that lower hydraulic resistance in the xylem hydraulic pathways (or the leaf-specific hydraulic conductance) of older trees allows for more rapid replenishment of water in leaves. While several studies have provided evidence for vessel diameter and length scaling with tree size [52,53], xylems are known to become more vulnerable to cavitation with cambial age, potentially reducing their ability to transport water [54–57]. According to [49], a decline in A with tree age is also accompanied by a decrease in g_s , which matches our own observations of low g_s in old trees. Low g_s is associated with reduced transpiration, as indicated by the reduced decline in midday Ψ in our own results. In contrast to our results, however, ref. [49] recorded lower Ψ in older *Acer* sp., with the authors suggesting that stomatal closure was being used as a protective mechanism to maintain minimum Ψ , thereby avoiding xylem cavitation and the loss of leaf turgor in older plants. The decline in g_s and the increase in Ψ in our study suggest that xylem hydraulic limitations are not the only reason for the decrease in A .

Ref. [58] showed that g_s was mainly determined by two leaf physiological parameters, i.e., stomata density and size. Any decrease in stomatal density, or increase in their size, leads to a decline in photosynthesis capacity and g_s [59]. While there is no clear evidence available on how stomatal traits change throughout oak ontogeny, mature Mediterranean oaks have been shown to have significantly lower stomatal density and a greater stomatal pore index and stomata pore length than seedlings [60]. Ref. [61] compared g_s in old (120-year-old) and young (10-year-old) southern beech *Nothofagus* sp. and found that g_s in old trees was up to 24% lower. In our own study, the difference in g_s between young and old oaks was noticeably larger, owing to the greater age difference between the trees (ca 600 years). Most studies have demonstrated increases in leaf thickness, density, and cell wall thickness with tree age, often quantified as an increase in leaf mass per area [5,34,49,62]. Such changes in leaf structure play a key role in decreasing internal CO_2 conductance and increasing the light compensation point and mitochondrial respiration [63]. In the same way, a study comparing tall (old) and short (young) southern beech indicated a decline in mesophyll conductance with tree size (age), though the effect was less than that with g_s [61]. The leading role of leaf structural traits in determining mesophyll conductance and net CO_2 assimilation has also been confirmed by [64,65] using a range

of *Quercus* sp. On the other hand, evidence from several studies suggests that mesophyll conductance may decline with increasing water stress stretching over periods of several days to weeks [63]. As younger trees naturally exhibit a lower Ψ than older trees, it remains unclear which process primarily affects mesophyll conductance. Taken together, the physiological changes mentioned above can modify diffusional resistance between the atmosphere and chloroplasts; thus, age-related morphological and anatomical changes in the leaf may lead to a decrease in photosynthetic capacity [4]. It should be noted that physiological indices such as Ψ , g_s , or A exhibit significant variability throughout the vegetation season. The findings regarding water relations and photosynthesis obtained in this study at two discrete points of the vegetation season necessitate verification through consecutive measurements encompassing various stages of leaf phenology and diverse intensities of drought.

However, anatomical changes in leaf internal structure and changes in stomatal size and density are not the only reasons for declining maximum g_s in large trees. Ref. [62], for example, recorded an increase in leaf waxiness and circular ledges over stomata with increasing tree age. This increase in leaf waxiness could potentially occlude stomata pores in older trees, leaving only a small aperture for the diffusion of CO_2 . Further, a thick epicuticular wax layer does not always mean better protection against desiccation and can even restrict stomatal closure [66]. In our study, minimum nighttime g_s was higher in older trees, presumably due to either the inability of old trees to tightly close stomata or the high permeability of the cuticle [67].

While water shortage events are expected to increase in the face of ongoing climate change, the potential effects of such shortages on veteran trees remain highly uncertain [68]. Our study demonstrates that while reduced stomata flexibility in old oaks increased water loss and limited the CO_2 fixation rate, reducing tree vitality, it may also promote water use efficiency, which, together with deeper root systems, may contribute to drought resistance [69]. In contrast, a higher minimum g_s than younger trees may jeopardise veteran trees' survival during drought periods. The response of such large old trees to rising CO_2 concentrations in the atmosphere also remains unclear. For example, while elevated CO_2 may contribute to stomata closure by decreasing stomata density, it also enhances CO_2 fixation, enhancing tree growth [70].

5. Conclusions

The decline in the vitality of veteran trees is one of the key issues in urban forestry. In our study, age affected the photosynthesis and water status of veteran oaks. While the level of photosynthesis was lowered in old trees, they exhibited improved access to soil water. Analysis of their chlorophyll fluorescence and photosynthetic biochemistry indicates that pedunculate oaks are capable of maintaining optimal light and carbon reactions into senescence. Conversely, their photosynthesis was primarily limited by maximum stomatal conductance. Their elevated minimum nighttime stomatal conductance suggests that veteran oaks may be susceptible to drought due to an inability to fully close their stomata. However, veteran trees exhibited improved access to soil water, potentially mitigating the effects of drought. Consequently, veteran trees may represent unique organisms that have adapted over their lifespan to function effectively in the face of ongoing climate change, despite having begun their lives long before the onset of current climate warming.

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